

Affordable and Trustworthy Remote Onboarding: Finding Solutions from Computer Vision Domain

Alpay Sabuncuoglu, Mark Hooper, Carsten Maple

The Alan Turing Institute, UK

Abstract. Supporting universal access to legal identity has emerged as a prominent global objective, garnering significant investment from governments, NGOs, research institutes, and companies. To accelerate ID registration processes, governments employ various programs, such as setting up temporary registration centers or visiting remote villages equipped with mobile registration kits. A more affordable alternative is developing a remote mechanism that can enable citizens to utilize their existing mobile phones to onboard themselves onto an identity system. The affordability in this context includes two main components: (1) Being accessible to travel-restricted citizens, (2) Achieving cost-effectiveness by utilizing already-in-use mobile devices. In addition to affordability, trustworthiness is a major issue in realizing a remote onboarding process due to the current technical capabilities of machine learning models and mobile devices.

This paper addresses these concerns related to affordability and trustworthiness by providing insights from recent state-of-the-art computer vision models to make informed technological decisions for possible solutions. Further, we discuss the usability and privacy-related concerns of the AI-powered components from the recent Human-AI interaction guideline perspectives. The primary objective of this report is to align the requirements of the registration context with the existing body of open-source research. We specifically focus on an example scenario in which mobile devices are leveraged to collect biometric information, enabling the establishment of a remote onboarding mechanism for citizens facing travel constraints.

1. Introduction

Universal access to legal identity is a pressing global objective, with significant investments from governments, NGOs, research institutes, and companies. The *Identification for Development* (ID4D) initiative focuses on providing identification systems and legal identities to individuals lacking them, primarily targeting developing nations [1]. This initiative prioritizes the advancement of inclusive and trustworthy identification systems that enable access to vital services, social protection, and economic opportunities. To assist countries in evaluating the condition of their identification systems and identifying areas for enhancement, ID4D Diagnostics offers a comprehensive system analysis and lists strengths and weaknesses. These diagnostic reports can benefit countries in pinpointing priority intervention areas, formulating strategies to enhance their identification systems, and working toward the establishment of inclusive and robust systems for all citizens.

Governments have explored various methods, including setting up temporary registration centers and using mobile registration kits in remote areas to address the challenge of affordability and accessibility in identity registration [2, 3]. A more cost-effective and widely accessible approach is to leverage existing smartphones and tablets to establish a remote onboarding mechanism for citizens facing travel constraints. However, ensuring the trustworthiness of such biometric technology is crucial for a reliable identification system. While determining the

biometric modalities in the registration process, ID4D suggests considering five main criteria for decision-makers [3]:

- (i) **Accuracy and Stability:** False acceptance rate (FAR) and false rejection rate (FRR) should demonstrate consistent accuracy for different cases considering inclusivity.
- (ii) **Inclusiveness:** The biometrics should be universal, accessible, and usable. For example, fingerprints can be damaged, which can lead to a failure to enroll (FTE), so decision-makers should consider alternative scenarios.
- (iii) **Collectability:** The collected biometric data should be of good quality and should decrease the vulnerability of the modality to fraud.
- (iv) **Acceptability:** The public should show openness to the use of the modality.
- (v) **Cost:** Hardware and software costs should be affordable for citizens and governments.

Considering these criteria, this paper presents an example scenario for a remote onboarding mechanism. In this scenario, a citizen can remotely register by introducing documents and collecting fingerprint photos and face images for biometric registration. Yet, to achieve this kind of registration process, we need trustworthy and affordable solutions that can demonstrate highly accurate, consistent recognition results in real-life cases. The components in this scenario are informed by analyzing the needs reviewed in ID4D Diagnostics and success stories from different countries, including India, Malawi, Ivory Coast, and Singapore. Further, the components are built upon the existing registration processes to support interoperability. The registration scenario integrates more affordable components to increase the accessibility of the registration process for citizens who might have challenges to travel registration centers.

As an initial step towards achieving a more affordable and trustworthy remote registration mechanism, this paper reviews recent research in the computer vision field that presents state-of-the-art or near-state-of-the-art results that can support using smartphones and tablets for biometric data collection. Overall, the example registration scenario includes three computer-vision-based solutions in this scenario: (1) Document understanding to extract information from available documents, (2) Contactless fingerprint collection and matching to obtain secure biometrics, (3) Face recognition and liveness detection to helper tool to support biometric identification. For each computer-vision-based solution identified, we analyzed the available datasets, summarized the main working mechanisms of the models, and explored how they can be adapted to work within our specific remote onboarding scenario. By integrating insights from this review into our proposed solution, we aim to align the requirements of the registration context with the advancements in state-of-the-art computer vision technologies.

In addition to computer-vision based solutions, we also integrated the "*Introducer*" concept which is used to formally vouch for a citizen that they know but who has no way of proving who they are [4]. Integrating this kind of mechanism can improve the overall accessibility by providing the means whereby the citizen or the introducer can use a mobile device and follow a process that enables self-verification and for them to also provide witness to the citizen's existence. This process supports the capturing of some level of biometrics in the process, which could be sufficient to provide a full or provisional identity for the citizen. Although developing such a solution relies on legislative and technological regulations, this paper is only focusing on the technology development process with open-source opportunities.

In this paper, we present a conceptual illustration of how leveraging current state-of-the-art computer vision models can increase the affordability of biometric collection scenarios by supporting the use of widely accessible smartphones and tablets. We demonstrate how each identified tech-based solution can be adapted to enhance the affordability of our remote onboarding mechanism. By combining insights from recent research with the specific needs of inclusive legal identity systems, we contribute to the development of innovative and reliable

biometric technology. Through this interdisciplinary approach, we seek to lay the foundation for a secure, trustworthy, and cost-effective remote onboarding mechanism that enables universal access to legal identity, benefitting citizens from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds and locations.

2. Understanding Challenges: ID4D Diagnostic Reports

Figure 1. The African countries that are included in ID4D Diagnostic Reports and their headline summaries that report the main challenge related to their registration processes. The background map of Africa in watercolor is generated using Stamen Maps [36].

The ID4D Diagnostics reports provide comprehensive, country-specific assessments that shed light on the current status and challenges faced by identification systems in various African countries [1]. These reports serve as valuable resources for policymakers, development practitioners, and other stakeholders, offering insights into the crucial issues and opportunities for enhancing identification systems in each country. In the first step of our scenario-building process, we tried to understand the country-specific issues related to registration processes. ID4D Diagnostics are available for sixteen countries, including Botswana, Burkina Faso, Cote d’Ivoire, Ethiopia, Guinea, Kenya, Liberia, Madagascar, Morocco, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Tunisia, Uganda, and Zambia. Figure 1 summarizes country-specific challenges for ID registration, including the ID registration rates for age over fifteen citizens.

Considering these country-specific challenges, we summarized our notes from these diagnostic reports under four main challenges, which are primarily associated with ID registration schemes:

- **Identification as a Potential Source of Conflict:** One key challenge revolves around the concept of "identification" itself, which can sometimes become a source of conflict.

Different stakeholders may have varying perspectives and interests, leading to debates and disagreements regarding the scope, criteria, and implications of identification processes. For example, in Cote d'Ivoire, after the coup, the identity issue has become a tension point between different stakeholders.

- **Limitations in Legislative Regulations:** Another challenge stems from the limitations within legislative regulations governing identification systems. Existing laws and regulations may fail to adequately cover all relevant issues, leaving gaps or ambiguities that can hinder the effective implementation and operation of the systems.
- **Reliance on Physical ID Centers:** Many identification systems still rely on physical centers for the registration and maintenance of ID records. This dependency on centralized locations can create logistical challenges, particularly in remote or underserved areas, where access to these centers may be limited or impractical.
- **Serving Communities with Restricted Traveling Abilities:** A significant opportunity lies in addressing the needs of communities with restricted traveling abilities. This includes individuals with disabilities, those from low socioeconomic backgrounds, and marginalized communities. Designing inclusive identification systems that consider their unique requirements can contribute to greater accessibility and equity.

These four main challenges demonstrate that the identity registration issue both needs policy/legislation level solutions and technology-related solutions. In this paper, our focus is *technology-related* solutions that can ease the registration process for communities with restricted access to travel due to economic or social disadvantages. Considering these technology-related challenges and analyzing the existing registration stages (Section 3), we developed our remote onboarding scenario (Section 4).

3. Existing Registration Processes: The Case of MOSIP

MoSIP (Modular Open Source Identity Platform) is an open-source platform designed to enable the development and deployment of scalable and interoperable identification systems. The registration process can be summarized in eight main steps [2]: **(1)** *Registration point setup* to establish physical or digital registration points where individuals can provide their personal information and biometric data. **(2)** *Applicant information collection* gathers the necessary personal details from the applicant. **(3)** *Document verification* to check the authenticity and validity of the applicant's supporting documents. **(4)** *Biometric enrollment*, which includes fingerprints, facial images, and sometimes iris scans. **(5)** *Data validation and quality assurance* validates the collected data for accuracy, consistency, and completeness. **(6)** *Data entry and system integration* involves entering the applicant's data into the system and associating the collected information and biometric data with a unique identifier or reference number. **(7)** *Identity provisioning* generates a unique identification number or card for the applicant, linking it to their registered information and biometrics within the system. Finally, **(8)** *enrollment acknowledgment* step provides the applicant with an acknowledgment receipt or confirmation of their successful enrollment.

In our example scenario, we are focusing on *technology-related* challenges that can be part of our remote onboarding process (**Steps 3, 4, and 5**), where the system collects information using available documents, enrolls the biometrics of citizens, validates these data, and performs de-duplication.

3.1. Information Collection

Personal Details: Collect essential personal information from the applicant, including their full name, date of birth, address, and any other relevant demographic information. Some

citizens might not have access to or knowledge of this information. The system should support registration with different levels of knowledge to make the system more inclusive.

Supporting Documents: Verify and record the details from supporting documents such as identity cards, passports, birth certificates, or any other required documentation based on the system's requirements. Allowing citizens to present different types of documents can increase the inclusiveness of the overall registration process.

3.2. Biometric Enrollment

Fingerprint Capture: Use fingerprint scanners to capture the applicant's fingerprints. This typically involves capturing multiple fingerprints, such as all ten fingerprints or a subset of fingers to ensure accurate biometric matching. Currently, most registration processes collect fingerprints via contact-based sensors, which some citizens might not want to touch due to health concerns and are more expensive in terms of hardware.

Facial Image Capture: Capture a high-quality photograph of the applicant's face using a digital camera or webcam. This image is used for facial recognition purposes. It is a less common biometric compared to fingerprint collection, as matching facial images is a more challenging task and more open to fraud. But it can be a helper mechanism in cases where the citizen cannot provide fingerprints.

3.3. Data Validation

Data Consistency and Duplicate Check: Verify the consistency and accuracy of the collected information by checking for any discrepancies or errors. Compare the collected data against existing records to identify potential duplicates and prevent multiple registrations for the same individual. Existing solutions include feature-based comparisons such as minutiae matching in traditional fingerprint de-duplication and machine learning (ML) based solutions that run black-box algorithms in the face de-duplication.

4. Example Remote Onboarding Scenario

The example scenario is built upon the MOSIP registration process to support interoperability but integrated more affordable components to increase the accessibility of the registration process for citizens who might have challenges to travel registration centers. Each component that we included for increasing the affordability of the system is inspired by success stories in different countries. Malawi has successfully integrated the "Document Scoring" system in which they supported the use of multiple documents to prove identity [4]. In India, when they lack these documents, they use the *Introducer* concept [5]. In Singapore and Ivory Coast, they are already using biometrics in mobile applications. [6, 7]. Figure 2 illustrates the main steps of this remote registration, where citizens can use their mobile phones to register themselves for the first time.

In this scenario, we assume that the citizen has already been informed that by using our application, they can obtain their legal identity to access basic services. The scenario considers different levels of access to technology and previous documentation. If the citizen has no access to a camera phone, they can continue registration with an *Introducer*. Introducers are used to formally vouch for a citizen that they know but who has no way of proving who they are. It is a concept that has already been active in Aadhaar registration in which a government-approved person can vouch for the citizen's identity [4]. Similar to Aadhaar's *Introducer* concept, the citizen can complete the steps using the *Introducer's* phone to register for ID without having her formal ID.

If the citizen has access to some legal documents, such as a birth certificate, a tax certificate, a personal testimony from the village head, etc., they scan these documents via camera. Then, they enter biographic information such as their name, date of birth, and address. Similar to

Figure 2. The example registration scenario for affordable remote onboarding. The components are linked with the countries (India, Malawi, Ivory Coast, and Singapore) that demonstrated successful applications of these technologies/concepts.

document scanning, the next step includes scanning biological biometrics such as fingerprints and the face. Overall, we present three computer-vision-based solutions in this scenario:

- (i) **Gather and upload the documents:** These documents prove the claimed identity. If the citizen has a camera phone, s/he can capture the documents using the camera and upload them.
- (ii) **Fingerprint collection:** The mobile camera can be used for contactless fingerprint collection.
- (iii) **Face recognition:** The mobile camera can capture the face and run on-device liveness detection.

Utilizing current state-of-the-art computer vision models can increase the affordability of biometric collection scenarios by supporting the use of smartphones and tablets. To inform the design of trustworthy and affordable biometric technology, we reviewed papers from 2014-2023 with open-source code that presents state-of-the-art or near-state-of-the-art results. Our emphasis on open-source models is to make our scenario both more accessible and maintainable. These machine learning repositories have a growing user base, which makes them more secure and easy-to-implement in an affordable way. We used the PapersWithCode database to find these papers using the following task keywords: "Document Understanding," "Key Information Extraction," "Fingerprint Recognition," "Fingerprint Matching," "Face Recognition," "Liveness Detection," "Face Anti-Spoofing." In this paper, for each computer-vision-based solution, we identified the available datasets, summarized the main working mechanisms of the models, and presented a conceptual illustration that can work in our scenario.

In the following sections (Section 5, 6, 7), we reviewed recent advances in our key computer vision domains. For each domain, we first listed the available datasets, then summarized the

state-of-the-art open-source models, described the evaluation metrics and use cases, and finally discussed the challenges and next steps.

5. Domain 1: Document Understanding/Information Extraction

When a citizen has access to previous documentation, such as an old birth certificate, electric bill, or tax certificate, ID issuers can use these documents to prove the citizen’s identity. However, the documents provided can be in multiple formats card-shaped, certificate, or handwritten on paper. Further, name, photo, date of birth (DoB), and other required information can be in different positions on the document.

Understanding all this information in a document- and language-agnostic way can improve the reading quality in many regions around the world, which can result in a decrease in the manual labor required and make the process more cost-effective.

Model	F1-Score on FUNSD
LayoutLMv3	92.63%
GeoLayoutLM	89.45%
LiLT	85.74%

Table 1. *Domain 1:* State of the art results on FUNSD dataset with F1-score comparison.

5.1. Available Datasets

CORD [7], Kleister [8], FUNSD [9], EPHOIE [10], ETD500 [11], and MIDV500 [12] are some available open-source datasets that can be used to train document understanding models. The datasets encompass a diverse range of applications within document understanding and information extraction. These datasets include resources for tasks such as geometric pretraining for visual information extraction, key information extraction from long documents with complex layouts, form understanding and extraction from noisy scanned documents, visual information extraction in real-world scenarios, metadata extraction from scanned electronic theses and dissertations, and identity document analysis and recognition on mobile devices through video streams. Although most of these datasets are not directly related to identity registration, we can use these datasets to understand the layout information and train our models to learn information extraction in a document and language-agnostic way. There is a growing body of research and available scanned documents in different languages and scripts.

5.2. State-of-the-art open-source models

Current successful models rely on transformer-based architectures that use multimodal data as training input. GeoLayoutLM [7] is a multimodal approach that learns geometric representations and the relation of entities. Another open-source model, LiLT [13], presents a transformer architecture for a language-independent understanding of structured documents. Although it is trained on documents in the English language, its model can be fine-tuned with relatively small data to learn information extraction in other languages. Combining these state-of-the-art models with the recent advances in large language models (BERT [14], GPT [15], etc.), we can extract semantically meaningful relational information from multiple documents in an unsupervised fashion. For example, LayoutLMv2 [16] combines the image information, positional encodings, and language information in transformer architecture. Later, they improved their model (LayoutLMv3 [17]) and achieved the current state-of-the-art results in the FUNSD dataset.

Although most of these models are trained with scanned documents, where documents are highly readable, when a citizen uses a camera to capture the document, it is not always a clear picture. So, it is also important to understand "quality" vs "readability." Here, we do not seek

for high resolution but obtain a highly readable version of the document. So, we can also run on-device blur detection before sending the document.

Figure 3. Conceptual model illustration for document understanding and information extraction model.

5.3. Evaluation metrics and use cases

In a digital ID use case, we expect the model to result in the information of interest with the position on the document. So, issuers can easily verify the information by checking the documents. The domain uses entity-level F1 scores for evaluation, which also resonates with our goal. For visual question answering (VQA) tasks, LayoutLMv2 uses Average Normalized Levenshtein Similarity (ANLS), where the metric considers the OCR imperfections.

5.4. Challenges and next steps

We can list two main needs and future directions: (1) The existing models have the capacity to speed up the information control process and make it more cost-effective. The research domain needs datasets for low-resource languages to fine-tune the existing models or to include them in the training process. (2) Limited models are available for on-device inference, which can allow more privacy-focused applications that can authenticate the documents and send the necessary information without uploading the documents to servers.

6. Domain 2: Fingerprint Collection and Matching

Fingerprints have been one of the most popular biometric mechanism due to the uniqueness of features and accuracy of recognition. Existing national ID solutions mostly depend on centralized identification systems with fingerprint identification. This kind of mechanism requires first capturing the fingerprint, then checking the fingerprint with the previous recordings (de-duplication). If fingerprint images are acquired from different fingerprint sensors, interoperability can be an issue. Existing solutions mostly depend on contact-based fingerprint sensors and mainly utilize minutiae features (unique patterns such as loops, arches, or whorls, etc.) for the de-duplication process.

Model	FAR per thousand
Carney et al. (8 fingers)	1
Carney et al. (Only index finger)	29
Lin and Kumar (Four fingers)	72

Table 2. *Domain 2:* State of the art results on their own collected datasets with different fingersets. Unfortunately, the field use different datasets and success metrics, which restricts the objective comparison.

6.1. Available Datasets

Publishing an open-source, public fingerprint dataset is a challenging task due to privacy issues, but the field already has some available real-life and generative datasets. Yet, recent work in the field produced both real and sythetic datasets, such as IIITD SmartPhone Finger-Selfie Database [18], Social-Media Posted Finger-selfie (SMPF) Database [18], Clarkson Fingerprint Generator [19], Contactless 2D to Contact-based 2D Fingerprint Images Database [20].

Figure 4. Conceptual model illustration for contactless fingerprint biometric collection and de-duplication.

6.2. State-of-the-art open-source models

The smartphone camera can provide good-enough resolution for collecting fingerprints. The key concern of acquiring fingerprints using a contactless mechanism is matching the previously collected contact-based fingerprints in the de-duplication process. Carney et al.’s smartphone-based fingerprint capture system follows a sequential mechanism in which the system detects the fingertips, segments each finger, applies filter-based enhancements such as Gabor and Adaptive Histogram Equalization filters and finally matches the fingerprints [21]. To test their approach, third-party assessors conducted experiments and achieved a 92% average pass rate in a database of 33 subjects with a total number of 275 Multi-Finger Touchless images. Lin and Kumar [22] propose the combination of two deformation correction algorithms to improve the matching accuracy of fingerprints acquired by different sensors: Robust thin-plate spline (RTPS) and deformation correction model (DCM). RTPS more accurately models elastic fingerprint deformations using splines, and DCM accurately aligns key minutiae features of contactless and contact-based fingerprints. The combined model achieved 94.11% rank-1 accuracy in which 1800 2D contactless fingerprint images and contact-based fingerprints from 300 distinct fingers were compared.

Both models are robust and lightweight compared to the models we examined in the previous domain (*Document Understanding/ Info Extraction*) review. A conceptual model is illustrated in the below figure, where we combined different solutions in the literature. Although the model details might change, the flow provides an interoperable application space by producing standardized and usable outputs after each step.

6.3. Evaluation metrics and use cases

Compared to document understanding tasks, fingerprint matching is a Pass/Fail situation. Thus, the False Accept Rate (FAR) (it is more important than the false reject rate as it is hard to recover from) and Equal Error Rate appear as the main metrics.

6.4. Challenges and next steps

Comparing the success of different models is challenging since the researchers use different datasets and metrics to evaluate their models. In addition, trustworthy matching of contactless and contact-based biometrics is the main challenge of supporting both mechanisms in a registration process. Collaboration with the industry is needed to achieve precision matching.

7. Domain 3: Face Features and Liveness Detection

Utilizing face biometrics presents significant challenges in achieving reliable recognition accuracy for individual identification. Face anti-spoofing is an emerging research area that directly influences the reliability of face authentication systems. Currently, the industry adopts face recognition as an additional mechanism to streamline login and validation processes instead of relying solely on face recognition as a standalone validation method.

Model	HTER on Replay
Sergievskiv et al.	0%
Yu et al.	1.7%
Wu et al.	7.1%

Table 3. *Domain 3:* State of the art results on Replay Attack dataset with HTER scores comparison.

7.1. Available Datasets

Replay-Attack [23], MSU-MFSD [24], Flickr-PAD [25], CASIA-MFSD [26] are some available open-source datasets that can be used to train liveness detection models. The datasets have different levels of complexity that cover different mechanisms of attacks. Common attacks include 2D photos and digital screens, and 3D masks of different qualities.

7.2. State-of-the-art open-source models

Although some feature-based, interpretable models achieve competitive accuracy [27, 28], current state-of-the-art models utilize deep-learning architectures. Some research focuses on utilizing generative methods like generative-adversarial networks (GAN) and variational autoencoders (VAE) to use the learning power of discriminators to learn attacks. For example, Wu et al. [29]’s model can preserve the spoofing-specific patterns in the generated spoofing images by learning a joint distribution of the identity representation and the spoofing patterns in the latent space. This mechanism guarantees the identity consistency of the generated paired images. Although the generative models produced promising results so far, current state-of-the-art models use semi-supervised learning approaches in which the training process leverages unlabeled data in both task-agnostic and task-specific ways. Sergievskiy et al.’s EntryV2 model [30] utilizes Chen et al.’s [31] unsupervised pretraining method [30], which the below figure summarizes conceptually, and proposes a multi-class auxiliary classification layer for augmenting the binary classification task of detecting spoofing attempts with explicit interpretable signals. This model achieves 0% HTER on Replay-Attack and MSU-MFSD. Although this model presents state-of-the-art results in most datasets, one key challenge lies in detecting replay attacks in unseen scenes. Tu et al. [32] address this challenge by introducing the Total Pairwise Confusion (TPC) loss, which enhances the generalizability of convolutional neural network (CNN) training. Additionally, they incorporate a Fast Domain Adaptation (FDA) component to mitigate the adverse effects caused by domain changes.

Figure 5. Conceptual model illustration for information extraction in a document-agnostic fashion.

7.3. Evaluation metrics and use cases

As a biometric solution, face matching is also primarily using False Acceptance Rate (FAR) and False Rejection Rate (FRR) as main evaluation metrics. In addition, the models use Half the Total Error Rate (HTER), which is the average of two error rates.

7.4. Challenges and next steps

The main challenge of face biometrics is attacks and defenses are developing together iteratively. Compared to document understanding and fingerprint matching methods, developing a trustworthy face-based biometric is more challenging. In terms of real-time inference, the EntryV2 model’s distilled small model could achieve similar accuracy, which is promising for deploying on-device. Further, since it is a vision-heavy problem, we can utilize neural architecture search to deploy more effective models, similar to Yu et al.’s approach [33]. The use of generative examples is another challenge, which can augment the bias or cause de-learning of patterns when used in the training process extensively.

8. Usability, Explainability, and Trust Considerations

In this paper, our primary focus has been on exploring computer-vision-based solutions to enhance the affordability of remote onboarding scenarios. We also aim to make this scenario inclusive in which citizens can complete the registration process without entering information or scanning biometrics if they cannot provide them due to a lack of information or disabilities. For example, the citizen might need access to the necessary assets for completing the registration scenario, such as documents or a phone with a camera. In another case, the internet connection might not be reliable in many developing areas. Alternatively, collecting and verifying biological biometrics using the current ML models can cause trustworthiness issues from both government and public perspectives.

To ensure a usable and trustworthy system, we should carefully craft the interaction between the remote onboarding mechanism, AI tools, and the citizens involved. Transparent delivery of AI-powered decisions to stakeholders is essential, and to guide our design process and AI interactions, we have primarily relied on the Microsoft Human-AI Interaction Guidelines [34], and the Google People+AI Framework [35]. Both guidelines aim to provide designers and developers with principles and best practices for creating AI systems that are transparent, inclusive, and respectful of user autonomy to help teams design AI systems that amplify human abilities while maintaining human control and understanding.

The interaction flows below summarize the main steps of device-citizen interactions for each AI-powered component of our remote onboarding scenario with a specific emphasis on usability, explainability, and trust considerations:

- **Interaction flow through document scanning:** The device should assess the quality of documents and accepts only high-quality, readable documents. Thus, it is crucial for the device to clearly communicate information related to document readability. Once a high-quality document is captured, the device identifies and presents the regions of interest, prompting citizens to mark any additional relevant areas. Ensuring natural and clear communication between the device and the citizen is essential, particularly when explaining what constitutes a readable document and the type of information relevant to the document issuer. The citizen then verifies if the model correctly categorizes the information and selects the appropriate regions on the document.
- **Interaction flow through fingerprint collection:** The device provides clear instructions on where to place fingertips and guides the citizen in capturing a focused photo. The device also verifies the quality of the fingerprints and requests another set of captures if necessary. Citizens are encouraged to capture their fingerprints in good lighting and against a plain background. If they encounter difficulties or are unable to provide fingerprints, they have the option to skip this step, and at this point, a government official can be dispatched for assistance.
- **Interaction flow through face scan:** The device provides clear instructions on where to stay and guides the citizen in capturing a focused photo. Citizens are prompted to capture their faces in good lighting against a plain background. The device verifies liveness on-device and, if required, may request a video recording for added security.

Although these are different models and follow different interaction flows, they also share some common principles in terms of transparency, inclusivity, privacy, usability, and user empowerment, considering the guidelines:

- **Transparency and Control:** The user should be aware that AI technology is being used to process their sensitive documents. In our domain reviews, we focused on on-device inference to make the system protect the information without uploading to servers for further processing. Clearly explaining the purpose and benefits of using AI technologies is critical, as the systems rely on AI output to power the processes.
- **Inclusivity and Accessibility:** Design the application to be accessible to a diverse range of users, including those with disabilities. While considering these interaction flows, we accounted for scenarios in which citizens are unable to complete certain required steps. For instance, a document might be physically deformed, making it unreadable. In such cases, the citizen can select all areas related to the required information, and the app should inform the user that the process may take longer due to manual checks. Similarly, in cases where fingerprints are deformed due to a citizen's working conditions, citizens have the option to skip this step. In such scenarios, a government official may visit the citizen, or the government can provide temporary access to vital services through temporary codes.
- **Privacy and Security:** Identity-related documents and biometrics are highly sensitive data, so we should prioritize the highest level of data protection. Considering secure data transmission and storage methods and avoiding storing sensitive data on third-party devices are necessary steps to achieve more trustworthy systems. In addition, the app should clearly communicate the application's privacy policies and ensure user consent for data usage.
- **Error Handling and Explanation:** An AI-powered system can produce false results, or the model can encounter errors during scanning or processing. In these cases, the

application should provide informative and user-friendly error messages that explain the issue and suggest possible solutions. For example, if the lighting is not enough to process liveness detection, we can inform the user about this issue by avoiding technical jargon that might confuse users.

- **Guided and Iterative Approach:** Each AI-powered process should follow a step-by-step process to offer the option to review and confirm the extracted information before final submission, allowing users to correct any inaccuracies. For example, in document scanning, the application asks the user to correct the output or add new information after scanning.
- **User Education:** Finally, the trust can only be achieved when the user fundamentally understands the technology behind it. We can include a section or tutorial within the application that educates users about the benefits and limitations of AI-powered document scanning. This can help manage user expectations and build trust.

Considering usability, explainability, and trust considerations in the design process and aligning with the previous frameworks and guidelines, the remote onboarding solution can be both effective and user-friendly while maintaining trust and transparency in AI-powered decision-making.

9. Conclusion

This paper mapped recent research in the computer vision domain to address the requirements of an affordable remote onboarding mechanism. Our focus was centered on three key domains within the steps of a possible remote onboarding mechanism: Document Understanding, Contactless Fingerprint Collection and Matching, and Face Liveness Detection. In the domain of Document Understanding, we explored advanced techniques and methodologies that facilitate accurate interpretation and extraction of relevant information from identification documents. These models rely on advancements in optical character recognition (OCR), document segmentation, and data extraction from documents. A multimodal, document and language-agnostic mechanism for document understanding can play a vital role in streamlining the remote onboarding process by accelerating the fact-checking process conducted by human issuers. Contactless Fingerprint Collection and Matching emerged as another critical domain. We delved into the latest research endeavors aiming to capture fingerprints using mobile device cameras and matching them with the previous records, leveraging advancements in feature extraction, template matching, and deep learning techniques. Finally, we explored recent research in Face Liveness Detection, including facial dynamics, texture analysis, and depth information to distinguish live faces from spoofing attempts, contributing to the overall security of remote onboarding mechanisms.

The research in these three domains demonstrated promising approaches that can accelerate the development of a trustworthy and accessible remote onboarding mechanism. Yet, we also identified some challenges that we can summarize under three categories in order to develop better models: (1) More datasets in low-resource domains, (2) Techniques for on-device inference and privacy-preserving training techniques, (3) Shared evaluation metrics and datasets for better model comparison. Further, we should utilize existing human-computer and -AI interaction guidelines to manage accessible and inclusive interaction throughout the registration process.

The remote onboarding mechanism can enable individuals with limited travel capabilities, including those from marginalized communities or with disabilities, to easily obtain legal identities. By aligning recent research developments in computer vision with the specific needs of affordable remote onboarding, we believe that fully remote onboarding can become available for individuals seeking accessible and secure identification systems.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported, in whole or in part, by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation [INV-001309]. Under the grant conditions of the Foundation, a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Generic License has already been assigned to the Author Accepted Manuscript.

References

This paper uses icons from flaticon.com, designed by vectorsmarket15, lutfix, Creative Stall Premium, smashingstocks, FlexSolution, and dhtgicon, Valeria, juicy_fish.

- [1] World Bank. 2016-2022. ID4D Country Diagnostics, Washington, DC: World Bank License: Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 <https://id4d.worldbank.org/country-action/id4d-diagnostics>
- [2] MOSIP Docs. MOSIP Registration. 2023. <https://docs.mosip.io/1.1.5/modules/registration-client>
- [3] World Bank Group. 2018. Technology Landscape for Digital Identification, Washington, DC. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/199411519691370495/pdf/Technology-Landscape-for-Digital-Identification.pdf>
- [4] U. Rao. 2019. Population Meets Database: Aligning Personal, Documentary and Digital Identity in Aadhaar-Enabled India, South Asia: Journal of South Asian Studies, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 537–553, 10.1080/00856401.2019.1594065.
- [5] T. Malik. 2020. Malawi’s Journey Towards Transformation: Lessons from its National ID Project, Center for Global Development.
- [6] Singpass - Your Improved Digital ID’. <https://www.singpass.gov.sg/main/> (Jul. 11, 2023).
- [7] C. Luo, C. Cheng, Q. Zheng, and C. Yao, ‘GeoLayoutLM: Geometric Pretraining for Visual Information Extraction’. arXiv, Apr. 21, 2023. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2304.10759>
- [8] T. Stanisławek et al., ‘Kleister: Key Information Extraction Datasets Involving Long Documents with Complex Layouts’, 2021, pp. 564–579. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-86549-8_36.
- [9] G. Jaume, H. K. Ekenel, and J.-P. Thiran, ‘FUNSD: A Dataset for Form Understanding in Noisy Scanned Documents’. arXiv, Oct. 29, 2019. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1905.13538>
- [10] J. Wang et al., ‘Towards Robust Visual Information Extraction in Real World: New Dataset and Novel Solution’. arXiv, Jan. 24, 2021. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2102.06732>
- [11] M. H. Choudhury, H. R. Jayanthi, J. Wu, W. A. Ingram, and E. A. Fox, ‘Automatic Metadata Extraction Incorporating Visual Features from Scanned Electronic Theses and Dissertations.’ arXiv, Jul. 01, 2021. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2107.00516>
- [12] Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology (State University) et al., ‘MIDV-500: a dataset for identity document analysis and recognition on mobile devices in video stream’, Computer Optics, vol. 43, no. 5, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.18287/2412-6179-2019-43-5-818-824.
- [13] J. Wang, L. Jin, and K. Ding, ‘LiLT: A Simple yet Effective Language-Independent Layout Transformer for Structured Document Understanding’. arXiv, Feb. 28, 2022. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2202.13669>
- [14] J. Devlin, M.-W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, ‘BERT: Pretraining of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding’. arXiv, May 24, 2019. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>
- [15] T. B. Brown et al., ‘Language Models are Few-Shot Learners’. arXiv, Jul. 22, 2020. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2005.14165>
- [16] Y. Xu et al., ‘LayoutLMv2: Multimodal Pretraining for Visually-Rich Document Understanding’. arXiv, Jan. 09, 2022. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2012.14740>
- [17] Y. Huang, T. Lv, L. Cui, Y. Lu, and F. Wei, ‘LayoutLMv3: Pretraining for Document AI with Unified Text and Image Masking’. arXiv, Jul. 19, 2022. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2204.08387>
- [18] A. Sankaran, A. Malhotra, A. Mittal, M. Vatsa, and R. Singh, ‘On smartphone camera-based finger photo authentication,’ in 2015 IEEE 7th International Conference on Biometrics Theory, Applications, and Systems (BTAS), Arlington, VA, USA: IEEE, Sep. 2015, pp. 1–7. doi: 10.1109/BTAS.2015.7358782.
- [19] K. Bahmani, R. Plesh, P. Johnson, S. Schuckers, and T. Swyka, ‘High Fidelity Fingerprint Generation: Quality, Uniqueness, and Privacy’. arXiv, May 21, 2021. Accessed: Jun. 13, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2105.10403>
- [20] Chenhao Lin, Ajay Kumar, ‘Matching Contactless and Contact-based Conventional Fingerprint Images for Biometrics Identification’, IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, vol. 27, pp. 2008–2021, April 2018. <http://www4.comp.polyu.edu.hk/~csajaykr/fingerprint.htm>

- [21] L. A. Carney et al., 'A Multi-Finger Touchless Fingerprinting System: Mobile Fingerphoto and Legacy Database Interoperability', in Proceedings of the 2017 4th International Conference on Biomedical and Bioinformatics Engineering, Seoul Republic of Korea: ACM, Nov. 2017, pp. 139–147. doi: 10.1145/3168776.3168800.
- [22] C. Lin and A. Kumar, 'A CNN-Based Framework for Comparison of Contactless to Contact-Based Fingerprints', IEEE Trans.Inform.Forensic Secur., vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 662–676, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TIFS.2018.2854765.
- [23] N. Sergievskiy, R. Vlasov, and R. Trusov, 'Generalizable Method for Face Anti-Spoofing with Semi-Supervised Learning'. arXiv, Jun. 13, 2022. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2206.06510>
- [24] Di Wen, Hu Han, and A. K. Jain, 'Face Spoof Detection With Image Distortion Analysis', IEEE Trans.Inform.Forensic Secur., vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 746–761, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TIFS.2015.2400395.
- [25] D. Pasmino, C. Aravena, J. Tapia, and C. Busch, 'Flickr-PAD: New Face High-Resolution Presentation Attack Detection Database.' arXiv, Apr. 25, 2023. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2304.13015>
- [26] Z. Zhang, J. Yan, S. Liu, Z. Lei, D. Yi and S. Z. Li, "A face anti-spoofing database with diverse attacks," 2012 5th IAPR International Conference on Biometrics (ICB), New Delhi, India, 2012, pp. 26-31, doi: 10.1109/ICB.2012.6199754.
- [27] Z. Boulkenafet, J. Komulainen, and A. Hadid, 'face anti-spoofing based on color texture analysis'. arXiv, Nov. 19, 2015. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1511.06316>
- [28] Di Wen, Hu Han, and A. K. Jain, 'Face Spoof Detection With Image Distortion Analysis', IEEE Trans.Inform.Forensic Secur., vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 746–761, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TIFS.2015.2400395.
- [29] H. Wu, D. Zen, Y. Hu, H. Shi, and T. Mei, 'Dual Spoof Disentanglement Generation for Face Anti-spoofing with Depth Uncertainty Learning'. arXiv, Dec. 01, 2021. Accessed: Jul. 13, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2112.00568>
- [30] N. Sergievskiy, R. Vlasov, and R. Trusov, 'Generalizable Method for Face Anti-Spoofing with Semi-Supervised Learning'. arXiv, Jun. 13, 2022. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2206.06510>
- [31] T. Chen, S. Kornblith, K. Swersky, M. Norouzi, and G. Hinton, 'Big Self-Supervised Models are Strong Semi-Supervised Learners'. arXiv, Oct. 25, 2020. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2006.10029>
- [32] X. Tu et al., 'Learning Generalizable and Identity-Discriminative Representations for Face Anti-Spoofing'. arXiv, Jan. 16, 2019. Accessed: Jul. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1901.05602>
- [33] Z. Yu et al., 'Searching Central Difference Convolutional Networks for Face Anti-Spoofing'. arXiv, Mar. 09, 2020. Accessed: Jul. 13, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.04092>
- [34] S. Amershi et al., 'Guidelines for Human-AI Interaction', in Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, Glasgow Scotland Uk: ACM, May 2019, pp. 1–13. doi: 10.1145/3290605.3300233.
- [35] Google PAIR. People + AI Guidebook. pair.withgoogle.com/guidebook Published May 8, 2019. Updated May 18, 2021.
- [36] Map tiles by Stamen Design, under CC BY 4.0. Data by OpenStreetMap, under CC BY SA